

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5084553>
УДК 378.016:1

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Foundation for building the present educational philosophy of Vietnam

Abstract. Educational philosophy is the theoretical basis, methodology and the general principle governing educational activities, educational subjects, educational content, modes, forms and goals of education. From a general perception of educational philosophies, the article presents the foundations for building Vietnam present educational philosophy, including the goals of the society that Vietnam is building and the characteristics of Vietnamese people therein. Based on those foundations, the present Vietnamese educational philosophy is: national - democratic - comprehensive and modern.

Key words: Philosophy, education, educational philosophy

General understanding of educational philosophy. What is the educational philosophy? This question has various different answers. Currently, this is a big problem facing educators, leaders, education managers as well as scientists. The answer then, in any form, involves the most fundamental thing that is the purpose and principle of a particular education. Therefore, there are the concepts of Eastern educational philosophy, Western educational philosophy, Japanese educational philosophy, American educational philosophy and Vietnamese education philosophy. For a country, in each historical period, the educational philosophy also varies.

To determine the educational philosophy of a country, i.e the purpose of an education, the most important basis is the goal of the society that the country aims to. To be compatible with that society, what characteristics people should have as subjects and products of the society? Necessary characteristics of human in a society are determined by the goals of society. So, after

all, the goal of the future society is the most decisive factor in the construction of educational philosophy. Each society has its own educational philosophy. The educational philosophy will serve that society. Society poses a need that requires education to meet. And how well education meets that need and to what extent positively or negatively impacts the development of the society. And a country with the proper educational philosophy will decide whether education meets the given needs of society or not, having a positive impact on the development of society or not. When the society changes, it is required that educational philosophy must change also.

Educational philosophy is relatively stable in the absolute movement of society. Educational philosophy is stable, because in relation to an education, educational philosophy is the theoretical basis, methodology and the general principle governing educational activities, educational subjects, educational content, modes, forms and goals of education.

According to that general rule, to define the present Vietnamese educational philosophy, it is necessary to base on the goals of the new society that Vietnamese people are building, and necessary characteristics of people in that society.

The foundation for building Vietnamese educational philosophy

The goal of the new socialist society

The struggle for national independence in Vietnam was thoroughly implemented after the victory of April 30, 1975. Since then, the whole country has been unanimously building a socialist model, gradually realizing the interests of the working class, the working people and the national interests. However, the awareness of the Party and the people about this new social model was not complete immediately upon entering that society. In the period before 1986, the characteristics of the socialist model in Vietnam were not clearly defined. The former Soviet Union model seemed to be the only target we aim for. Entering the renovation period, from domestic and international economic, political and social realities, especially the socialist system, for the first time in the history of building socialism in Vietnam, six basic characteristics of socialist society in Vietnam were introduced by the Communist Party of Vietnam in its Platform on national construction in the period of transition to socialism, in 1991, at the 7th national Party congress. The six characteristics include: Ownership by the working people; Having a highly developed economy based on the modern production force and the public ownership over the main production materials; Having an advanced culture, imbued with national identity; People are liberated from oppression, exploitation and injustice, working on their abilities, enjoying on their labor, and having a life of prosperity, freedom, happiness, and conditions for comprehensive personal development. All ethnic groups in the country are equal, united and helping each other to progress together; Having friendly relations and cooperation with people all over the world. These six characteristics clearly indicate the goals and

dynamics of the process of building and developing the country along the socialist path in Vietnam.

After twenty years of renovation, the reality of renovation in Vietnam and other countries in the world is one of the bases that by the 10th national congress the Party identified more clearly and specifically about the characteristics of the socialism model in Vietnam. Accordingly, the society that the Party and people of Vietnam build is described as: Rich people--strong nation--equitable, democratic and civilized society; ownership by the people; having a highly developed economy, based on a modern production force and production relations consistent with the development level of the production force; having an advanced culture imbued with national identity; People are liberated from oppression and injustice, and have a full, free, happy life, having conditions to comprehensively develop; all ethnic groups in the Vietnamese community are equal, united, respecting and mutually helping each other to progress; having a socialist rule-of-law State of the people, by the people and for the people under the leadership of the Communist Party; having friendly relations and cooperation with people around the world" [1, p.68].

"That spirit has been incorporated into the National Construction Platform in the period of transition to socialism (supplemented and developed in 2011). *"The socialist society that our people builds is a society with: Rich people--strong nation--equitable, democratic and civilized society; ownership by the people; having a highly developed economy, based on a modern production force and production relations consistent with the development level of the production force; having an advanced culture imbued with national identity; People are liberated from oppression and injustice, and have a full, free, happy life, having conditions to comprehensively develop; all ethnic groups in the Vietnamese community are equal, united, respecting and mutually helping each other to progress; having a socialist rule-of-law State of the people, by the people and for*

the people under the leadership of the Communist Party; having friendly relations and cooperation with people around the world” [2, p. 70].

Thus, with three important milestones in the renovation era of Vietnam, i.e 1991, 2006 and 2011, the socialism model in Vietnam has been shaped. The road to socialism in Vietnam has passed the stage of tinkering and searching for a new model, in order to move to the realization of the new social model, realizing the characteristics of socialism. This model clearly shows the universality of socialism and the specificity of the socialism model in Vietnam. Outstanding values in the current socialist model are:

Firstly, human liberation.

Human being is a multi-level concept of individual and community (class, family, ethnic group, religion, country etc.) and mankind. The goal of socialism that Vietnam builds is to free people of all those levels. *People should have a good and happy life.* This only becomes a reality when people are freed from all oppression and unfair exploitation in relations between individuals, classes, ethnic groups, religions and nations. The origin of human liberation is to develop a production force at a high level of socialization, as a basis for establishing production relations, the core of which is social ownership of production materials. That is, human liberation, first and foremost, is to remove oppression, economic exploitation, and then to eliminate the political oppression and the human ideological and spiritual enslavement.

Human liberation is the combined value, covering all characteristics of the socialism model in Vietnam. Human liberation is both the goal and the driving force of the social development and the cause of building socialism of the Party and people of Vietnam. Economic development, political stability, construction of cultural and social life in Vietnam today are all geared towards ensuring the interests of people including individuals, communities, nations and humanity. On the contrary, it is the goal of

human liberation that has created a great motivation for all individuals, communities and nations to join forces and unanimously build the country under the leadership of the Party..

Second, comprehensive human development.

Human liberation will not be complete if in that liberation career, man has not developed comprehensively, he is not really free and owns himself. K. Marx and F. Engels, right from the work of the Communist Party's Declaration, affirmed that the purpose of the struggle of the working class and the working people is to build a society "in which the free development of each person is a premise for the free growth of all people” [3, p. 628].

Comprehensive human development here is understood as personal development in terms of power, mindset and mentality; literature, body, and beauty; intellectual, ethics, lifestyle and personality. It is to build Vietnamese people in the direction of honesty, goodness and beauty, "imbued with the national spirit, humanity, democracy and science.

Comprehensive human development, including the communal and national economic, political, cultural and social development. There, economic growth is associated with social justice, natural environment in harmony with the social environment, personal interests associated with community and social benefits et. "Rich people" goes with "strong country" and "a just, democratic and civilized society". "Rich people" but the country is not strong, the society is not just, democratic and civilized, then the "rich people" are unsustainable and just formality. On the contrary, "strong country" will be meaningless when it does not bring wealth to the people and society is not really just, democratic and civilized. The culture is advanced and modern, also fully preserving the identity of the Nation. That culture creates the strength for sustainable economic growth and a modern and civilized society. Just as stated in the Ninth Resolution

of the 11th Party Central Committee, *culture really becomes a solid spiritual foundation of society, an important endogenous strength to ensure sustainable development and firmly defend the Fatherland for the goal of rich people, strong country, democracy, justice and civilization.*

The foundation for comprehensive human development is *a highly developed economy, based on modern production forces and consistent production relations.*

Thirdly, to ensure human rights and democracy

Guarantee of human rights: to guarantee human interests and natural needs, which are inherent and objective, is the aspiration not only of socialism, but of all different stages of human society. Thus, from the *Declaration of Independence of the United States* in 1776, the *Declaration of the Human Rights and Civil Rights of France* in 1791 to the *Declaration of Independence of Vietnam*, President Ho Chi Minh affirmed that "Everyone is born with equal rights. The Creator gave them the rights that no one can invade, which includes the right to life, the right to freedom and the right to seek happiness." That is the reason no one denied. Therefore, when the country of Vietnam has become a free and independent country, "The entire Vietnamese people is determined to bring all spirit and force, life and wealth to maintain that freedom and independence" [3, p. 557].

According to the spirit of President Ho Chi Minh, the socialist model that the Party and people of Vietnam builds, human rights and citizenship must always be guaranteed. That is one of the goals in the cause of socialism building in Vietnam. Ensuring human rights, civic rights, not only in ideology and law, but also in practice. Human rights are expressed and concretized through the category of democracy which is a characteristic of socialist society in Vietnam, i.e a society of rich people, strong country, democracy, justice and civilization. Socialist democracy is the aspiration, the step forward, the highest development in the history of all forms of democracy. To achieve democracy,

building a socialist rule-of-law state of the people, by the people and for the people under the leadership of the Communist Party is in accordance with the law..

Human characteristics in the new society - socialist man

Man is the product and also the subject of history. Simultaneously, people create society and people are created by society. So, President Ho Chi Minh said "to have socialism, there must be socialist people."

Currently, the cause of building and developing the country along the socialist path in Vietnam is being influenced by many domestic and international factors with great advantages, opportunities and challenges. The process of globalization and international integration has been promoted, creating opportunities for Vietnam to expand cooperation relations with countries in the region and the world, thereby, exploiting Vietnam's advantages and taking advantage of other countries' experiences in economic, cultural and social development and keeping political stability. The modern science and technology revolution, the fourth industrial revolution (4.0), affects all fields of the economy, culture, as well as every human being and community in society. Ongoing achievements of the industrial revolution 4.0 stretch the hands and expand people's minds to prove that human power is endless, and Vietnamese society and people are no exception. Domestically, after more than 30 years of renovation, Vietnam's influence and international reputation in economics, politics, culture and society have been affirmed on the world map. In particular, the intelligence, capacity and personality of Vietnamese people in dealing with social crises (economic, financial, political, medical etc.) have made the world astonished. The national spirit is always hidden in each Vietnamese person, so that whenever the Nation faces unusual events, that spirit explodes to create a great strength of the nation.

However, besides the advantages and opportunities, Vietnam is still facing great challenges and risks; the risk of economic

lagging, the risk of "peaceful evolution" of the forces to oppose the cause of building socialism in Vietnam; the risk of recession in terms of politics, ideology, morality, lifestyle, "self-evolving" and "self-transforming" manifestations of a part of cadres and party members. There go peaceful international relations, cooperation, compromise, competition, mutual restraint, no longer confrontation between nations, but potentially it is the possibility of territorial disputes, natural resources, infringement of national sovereignty, religious conflict and cyber warfare etc. The above dangers and challenges seem to become more complicated when there is the relay of modern technological achievements, which creates a certain barrier to the process of realizing the goals of the new society in Vietnam.

In that situation, in order to successfully build a socialist model in Vietnam with the aforementioned characteristics as well as to enjoy the social values of that model, Vietnam needs to have "socialist" people with new, modern wisdom, capacities and qualities. Characteristics that are required for Vietnamese people, as the subject of socialist society include:

Firstly, humane people.

The humanity of Vietnamese people is the crystallization of patriotism (nationality), tolerance, altruism and a sense of responsibility towards the community and society. This is the identity of culture and people of Vietnam.

Patriotism is an inherent quality of people in any country or nation. In each historical era, that patriotic spirit is manifested by different actions. But, every action puts the protection of national interests first and foremost. Because only when the national interests are preserved, can the interests of individuals and communities be realized.

National spirit is the factor that creates the endogenous strength of Vietnamese nation. President Ho Chi Minh affirmed: "Our people have a passionate patriotism. That is a precious tradition of our people. From past to

present, when the Fatherland was invaded, that spirit was excited. It is combined into a very strong and big wave, it passed through all dangers and difficulties, it engulfed all those who betrayed or robbed the country". So, for President Ho Chi Minh and the people of Vietnam, it would rather sacrifice everything than lose the country, definitely not be a slave.

Currently, when the country moves to a new revolutionary stage of social construction and development. The patriotism and national spirit of Vietnamese people are expressed in their determination to develop the economy and society, and bring the country out of the state of poverty; fight to protect the people's revolutionary cause from the destruction of reactionary forces; preserve and promote the traditional values that create the identity of Vietnamese people, determined to make the country overcome challenges to realize the social model of rich people, strong country, democracy, justice and civilization.

Accompanying the national spirit is the tolerance, generosity, and altruism of the Vietnamese people towards things different from themselves, their nation or country. In the current trend of globalization, the world develops with a multi-polar trend, respect, understanding and prejudice against people, nations, countries that do not have the same political regime, economic level, culture and society are essential for cooperation and mutual development. That is also a necessary condition for Vietnam to integrate into the region and the world.

Secondly, creative people

Human nature is creativity. Thanks to creativity, people have been moving from being dependent on nature to gradually mastering it, recreating the second nature to serve human needs. Human creativity is the decisive factor for the continuous development of production forces as well as of society..

The cause of building socialism in Vietnam in particular and the world worker movement in general, more than ever, requires human creativity, since the socialist

model is not available in history, although the working people's need of being liberated is inherent in man. In the era of industrial revolution 4.0 today, the process of socialization of modern scientific and technological achievements takes place very quickly. The competition among people, between communities and countries to dominate modern technology achievements for development is extremely fierce. New manufacturing industries are formed on the basis of new technology achievements, bringing an extremely large volume of super profits. Along with that, some traditional industries will disappear. Modern technology revolution has more and more influence on human development and socio-economic development of countries..

In order to realize the socialist model in Vietnam, there must be Vietnamese people with creativity, flexibility, and constant innovation to adapt to the rapid changes of society and the world to take advantage of the achievements of the modern science and technology revolution, turning those achievements into a driving force for development. Otherwise, the risk of falling behind will soon become a reality.

Thirdly, modern people (including wisdom, living and working skills).

Building up the socialist model in the present era, so as for people to be creative and flexible, it is necessary to have modern people. In the near future, in order to build and develop the country, in association with the achievements of modern science and technology revolution, Vietnam will focus on key economic sectors, automation and high technology; strengthening cooperation between science and technology, production and business; deploying powerful and extensive application of new technologies in economic development and social life; expanding international cooperation in research, development and technology transfer etc. These key economic sectors will be strong catalysts for promoting the development of the whole economy, boosting

the "production force more and more modern", thereby building up "appropriate production relations".

Therefore, in the strategy of building and developing Vietnamese people, it is very important to pay attention to the training of high-quality human resources with high intellectual qualifications, expertise and wide cooperation capabilities. An architect not only needs to specialize in architecture, materials science, but also must be knowledgeable in biological sciences, anthropology etc. On the contrary, a scientist who studies in the social field not only needs knowledge, deep expertise to analyze the society. Without being able to take advantage of the achievements of science and technology, computer science etc. he will work much less effectively.

Present Vietnamese educational philosophy

The goal of a new society and characteristics of people in the future society shows that the educational philosophy needed to develop Vietnam's education today includes nation - democracy - comprehension - modernity. This is the rationale, principles that govern the goals, modes, forms, contents and programs of Vietnam's education. In which, the goal of Vietnamese education is: "To comprehensively develop Vietnamese people with ethics, knowledge, culture, health, aesthetics and profession; to have quality, capacity and sense of citizenship; to have patriotism, national spirit, loyalty to the ideal of national independence and socialism; to promote the potential and creativity of each individual; to improve people's knowledge, developing human resources, fostering talents, meeting the requirements of the cause of national construction and defense and international integration"(Article 2, Education Law, issued by the National Assembly of Vietnam in 2019). Based on that goal, to determine the form, mode and content of the program in Vietnamese education system as well as each educational level therein.

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Поступила в редакцию 09.06.2021.
Принята к публикации 12.06.2021.

Для цитирования:

Ngo Thi Phuong, Pham Quynh Chinh Foundation for building the present educational philosophy of Vietnam // Гуманитарный научный вестник. 2021. №6. С. 169-175. URL: <http://naukavestnik.ru/doc/2021/06/NgoThi.pdf>